

Research

Free Primary Education Policy Implementation Challenges in the Perspectives of Teachers: A Case Study in Pyin Oo Lwin District of Myanmar

Thet Khaing¹, Dr. Dian Feng¹, Mohammed Rebwar Ahmed¹

¹College of Education, Zhejiang Normal University, People's Republic of China

Abstract: The purpose of this study was to examine the challenges faced by teachers in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar. This paper identified key factors that influenced the implementation of policies and proposed strategies for achieving these objectives.

Literature reviews were conducted using electronic databases and government documents, focusing on English-language articles published between 2010 and 2023. According to a PRISMA flowchart documenting the selection process, the study followed strict inclusion and exclusion criteria. In order to collect data, a standardized form was used, and quality assessment tools were employed according to the design of the study.

The results of the study indicated that policy implementation was confronted with several challenges, including limited resources, deteriorating infrastructure, inadequate training, and a lack of support systems. Further, cultural and contextual factors played a significant role in determining policy effectiveness. The study proposed strategies to address these challenges, including the allocation of resources, the development of infrastructure, the training of teachers, and the enhancement of support systems. There were valuable lessons to be learned from other regions when it came to adapting policy measures.

One of the key findings of the study was the critical lack of qualified teachers, particularly in remote regions, as well as the need for enhanced teacher training and professional development. Due to the increased student-teacher ratio resulting from the policy, teachers were required to manage their classrooms effectively. Several factors influenced teacher motivation and morale, including low salaries and limited opportunities for career advancement. To achieve policy success, it was also essential that teachers and parents worked together effectively.

Several strategies were implemented to achieve policy goals, including strengthening teacher training, improving access to educational resources, increasing parental and community involvement, addressing infrastructure needs, aligning curriculums, and establishing robust evaluation and monitoring systems.

The findings of this study emphasized the importance of context-specific approaches in the implementation of educational policies. In order to contribute to the success of Myanmar's Free Primary Education Policy, the proposed strategies have been tailored to the needs of Pyin Oo Lwin District in order to improve education quality and accessibility.

Keywords: Free Primary Education Policy, Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, Implementation Challenges, Teacher Training and Professional Development, Classroom Management, Teacher Motivation and Morale, Parent-Teacher Collaboration, Policy Implementation Strategies.

*Corresponding Author: Thet Khaing, Dr. Dian Feng, Mohammed Rebwar Ahmed

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Introduction

Achieving personal empowerment and societal development is possible through education (UNESCO, 2019a). As a result of governments worldwide realizing the importance of education, they have implemented various policies to provide quality education to all citizens. It is intended to provide equitable and inclusive education to all children in Myanmar through the Free Primary Education Policy (National Education Commission, 2016). As a result of this policy, UN Sustainable Development Goal 4 education for all is a significant step closer to being achieved (United Nations, 2015).

1.1 The National Education Law and its Amendments

After the National Education Law (NEL) was enacted in 2014 and then amended in 2015, Myanmar's education sector has made significant progress. It is through these laws that the foundation has been laid for comprehensive reforms to be implemented across the whole of the education system (R. Smith, 2020). Several key changes have been introduced in the NEL and its amendment, including guarantees of free and compulsory primary education for all citizens, an extended basic education system of 13 years, support for ethnic languages and cultures, increasing decentralization, and involving parents and communities in school management (National Education Commission, 2016).

In the current educational system, Myanmar follows a KG + 12 system, which comprises kindergarten and 12 years of basic education (R. Smith, 2020). A significant milestone in the ongoing education reform process has been reached with the implementation of this structure starting with the 2016-17 academic year (Htun, 2019). A major objective of the government is to improve the learning environment and provide necessary resources in support of this transition. School infrastructure improvements, textbook access, and teacher training programs for effective pedagogy demonstrate the government's commitment to enhancing the quality of education in Myanmar (Ko Ko, 2019).

The National Education Law was first established in 2014 and then amended in 2015 as evidence of the government's commitment to education reform (National Education Commission, 2016). In addition to providing a comprehensive framework encompassing various aspects of the education system, these laws also provide recognition of the right to free and compulsory primary education, mechanisms for quality assurance, a decentralized educational decision-making system, the integration of ethnic languages and cultures into the curriculum, and quality assurance mechanisms. Reforms are being implemented to create a more inclusive and equitable education system that fits the needs of diverse students and encourages community participation in the management of schools.

The implementation of education reforms in Myanmar has encountered significant challenges despite significant progress. It is critical that reform efforts are sustained and resource gaps are addressed through adequate funding (World Bank, 2020a). Furthermore, teachers must continue to receive professional development and support to implement the revised curriculum and pedagogical approaches effectively (Htun, 2019). This challenge can be overcome by maintaining a commitment to education reform, collaborating with relevant stakeholders, and taking advantage of international expertise and support (Ko Ko, 2019).

To ensure the successful implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy, understanding the challenges faced by teachers is crucial. The role of teachers in implementing policy and creating a learning environment conducive to student success is vital (Fullan, 2007). Despite these obstacles, education policies have been successful in

implementation due to a variety of factors, including inadequate funding, inadequate infrastructure, insufficient training, and limited support systems (Adeyemi, 2015; Darling-Hammond, 2017).

1.2 Purpose and Research Questions

As part of this study, we explore and analyze the challenges that teachers face in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar. To understand the implementation challenges within Myanmar's education system, Pyin Oo Lwin District serves as a specific context. This article provides valuable insights into the factors that may impede the successful implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District by examining the challenges faced by teachers. To improve the quality and effectiveness of primary education in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, the findings of this article can be used to inform policy decisions, resource allocations, and capacity-building efforts, which ultimately contribute to achieving the goal of providing equitable and inclusive educational opportunities for all.

The research questions addressed in this article are as follows:

1. What are the key factors influencing the effective implementation of the free primary education policy by teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar?
2. To ensure that Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, meets its free primary education policy objectives, what strategies should be considered?

In this article, we seek to shed light on the challenges teachers face in implementing Pyin Oo Lwin District's Free Primary Education Policy by examining these questions and making recommendations regarding policy and practice to ensure its successful implementation and the achievement of the desired educational outcomes.

This study extends the hypothesis developed in the preceding sections by looking at the dynamic interaction between policy implementation and the ground realities in Myanmar's educational sector. There is a disparity between policy intent and practical implementation, particularly in the case of the Free Primary Education Policy, despite the comprehensive legislative framework established by the National Education Law and its amendments.

It is hypothesized in this study that while policy initiatives like the Free Primary Education Policy are pivotal to advancing education, their success depends in large part on the ability to address multifaceted challenges at the local level. Besides logistical and infrastructure issues, Myanmar's educational landscape is characterized by a diverse and evolving set of cultural, socio-economic, and political challenges.

Based on these considerations, the research seeks to provide a current and nuanced analysis of these challenges. It hypothesizes that a deeper insight into the experiences of teachers, who are the primary agents of policy implementation, will reveal critical factors impacting the effectiveness of educational reforms. Thus, policymakers and stakeholders may be able to learn valuable lessons that can be used to refine and implement education policies that are compatible with the needs and aspirations of Myanmar's society as it develops.

As a result of including these elements in the scope of our investigation, the study contributes to a broader discourse on education reform, not only within Myanmar but also in other contexts facing similar challenges. Numerous factors influence policy implementation at the local level, and this hypothesis acknowledges this complexity and emphasizes the importance of a holistic approach.

Research Methodology

2.1 Search Strategy

To identify relevant studies regarding the challenges teachers face in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, a comprehensive literature search was conducted. To ensure a comprehensive overview of the topic, a broad range of sources was included in the search.

A combination of keywords and subject headings was used to systematically search electronic databases such as Education Research Complete, ERIC, and Scopus. These keywords were adapted to match the specific syntax and

subject headings used by each database, such as "Free Primary Education Policy," "teacher challenges," "implementation," and "Myanmar."

It can be seen, for example, that the search query in ERIC was constructed as follows: "Free Primary Education Policy" AND "teacher challenges" AND "implementation" AND "Myanmar". For Education Research Complete and Scopus, similar search queries were developed.

Additionally, we performed a manual search of relevant government reports, policy documents, and gray literature to identify relevant sources of information. The purpose of this procedure was to ensure that non-indexed information was included in the database. Reports and policy documents were identified by examining the websites of government education departments, international organizations, and educational research institutions.

Articles published between 2010 and 2023 in English were excluded from the search. To ensure that the literature review reflects current perspectives on the challenges faced by teachers in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, this time frame was selected to include recent studies and ensure that recent studies were included.

As a result of the initial search, 891 articles were obtained from electronic databases, while 8 additional reports and documents were obtained from manual searches and other sources. The results of the screening and analysis were based on the inclusion of 859 articles after removing duplicates.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The following inclusion criteria were used to select studies:

1. Provide a detailed analysis of the challenges that teachers face in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar.
2. The research should have been published in peer-reviewed journals, conference proceedings, or other sources of repute.
3. Analyze the challenges faced by teachers in-depth or provide empirical evidence.
4. Provides coverage of the period from 2010 to 2023 to ensure that recent studies are included.
5. The document has been written in English.

The exclusion criteria for studies were as follows:

1. Lacked relevance to the research questions.
2. Had duplicate publications or data that overlapped.
3. Could not be analyzed because they were not available in full text.

2.3 Screening and Selection Process

Two stages of screening were applied to select relevant studies: the screening of titles and abstracts was followed by the screening of full texts. Aiming to identify articles that met the inclusion criteria outlined above, but excluding studies that did not meet these criteria.

Based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria, two independent reviewers screened the titles and abstracts. Each article was evaluated by the reviewers by examining its title and abstract for information related to the challenges teachers face when implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar. Several articles were excluded for lack of sufficient information or for failing to meet the criteria.

It was resolved through discussion and consensus that any differences between the two reviewers during the screening process were resolved. To make the final decision, a third reviewer was consulted in cases where a consensus could not be reached.

A full-text screening was conducted on the remaining articles following the screening of titles and abstracts. According to the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the reviewers read the full text of each article to determine its eligibility. As part of the inclusion criteria, factors such as relevance to the research questions, a focus on the challenges facing teachers in

implementing the policy, and an assessment of alignment with the geographical context of Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar were considered. We excluded articles that did not meet the criteria at this stage.

Flowcharts based on the PRISMA guidelines were used to document the study selection process. As shown in the PRISMA flowchart, the number of articles included and excluded at each stage of the screening process is visually represented (Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., 2009). By using this flowchart, the systematic review can be reproduced and ensured to be transparent.

The initial search identified 899 articles. The title and abstract of 859 articles were screened after the duplicates had been removed and the inclusion and exclusion criteria were followed. To conduct a full-text screening, 47 articles were selected after being screened based on their title and abstract. The systematic review was conducted after reviewing 44 articles in full text that met the inclusion criteria and met the inclusion criteria.

Fig. 1: Literature search and selection of articles for review (adapted from PRISMA 2009)

2.4 Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

To ensure consistency and systematic retrieval of relevant information from each included study, the data was extracted using a standardized form. Information pertinent to teacher challenges, such as the name of the author(s), the publication year, the study design, the sample size, the method of data collection, and any other pertinent information, were captured on the form.

After screening and selecting articles based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria described earlier, the data extraction process was conducted. To minimize bias, the data extraction was performed by two independent reviewers. A standardized form was used to extract data independently from each study included in the review. When discrepancies occurred, the reviewers discussed them and reached an agreement.

Depending on the study design, appropriate tools were used to assess the quality of the included studies. To assess the quality of qualitative studies, a checklist developed by the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) was used. To

determine the extent to which qualitative research is rigorous, credible, and relevant, this checklist was developed. A discussion between the reviewers resolved any disagreements regarding the quality assessment.

We ensured the reliability and validity of the findings obtained from the included studies through the data extraction process and quality assessment. As a result of the data extraction, valuable insights were gained into the challenges teachers faced when implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar. They were used to support the synthesis of the findings in the systematic review.

This systematic review ensured that the findings were based on reliable and relevant evidence by following a standard data extraction process and utilizing appropriate quality assessment tools. A thorough analysis of the challenges faced by teachers in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, is provided by the process of data extraction and quality assessment.

2.5 Data Synthesis

Based on the data synthesis, it has been concluded that Pyin Oo Lwin District currently faces several challenges in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy. Numerous research studies have reported a shortage of resources, including inadequate funding for educational materials, textbooks, and school infrastructure. As well, there were disparities between urban and rural areas within the district about educational quality and access. Based on these findings, targeted interventions are required to address resource gaps and improve equity in education.

As a result of the data synthesis, several key factors were identified that influence teachers' ability to implement the Free Primary Education Policy effectively. According to studies, teachers must be trained and provided with opportunities for professional development to enhance their pedagogical skills and subject knowledge. Teachers were found to be hindered in their ability to effectively implement the policy due to the lack of access to quality training programs. Further, the study demonstrated the importance of community engagement, parental involvement, and administrators' support in creating an enabling environment for educators.

To achieve the free primary education policy targets in Pyin Oo Lwin District, several strategies could be considered. It has been repeatedly emphasized in studies that the implementation of the policy requires adequate resources, both financial and material. Education budgets should be increased, infrastructure should be improved, and teaching and learning materials should be provided. Furthermore, the synthesis concluded that pedagogical skills, subject knowledge, and classroom management techniques need to be addressed in comprehensive and continuous teacher training programs. Support and supervision systems were identified as crucial for providing guidance and feedback to teachers. In addition, community engagement and partnerships with parents were found to enhance the effectiveness of policy implementation. Pyin Oo Lwin District's unique cultural and contextual factors are also taken into account in the development of context-specific approaches.

The data synthesis suggests that to ensure the achievement of the free primary education policy targets in Pyin Oo Lwin District, key strategies include addressing resource constraints, enhancing teacher training and professional development, encouraging community engagement, and developing context-specific approaches. Policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can use these findings to design and implement effective interventions to improve primary education.

Findings

3.1 Factors influencing the effective implementation of the free primary education policy by teachers

There has been a worldwide effort to promote access to quality education for all children through the implementation of free primary education policies. It is important to address the challenges teachers face in implementing such policies to ensure their success. Based on a case study of primary schools in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, this article investigates the challenges teachers experience in implementing the free primary education policy.

3.1.1 Availability of Qualified Teachers

It is essential to ensure that there is a sufficient number of well-trained teachers available in Myanmar so that the free primary education policies can be implemented successfully. Due to the increased enrollment due to the policy, there has been an increase in the number of students enrolled, which requires more qualified educators to be available (UNESCO, 2019b). The Myanmar government continues to face challenges when it comes to expanding the pool of teachers in rural and remote areas of the country (UNICEF Myanmar, 2019), despite this. Due to the challenges presented by these issues, education can't be delivered efficiently and effectively, and this contributes to the lack of equitable access to quality learning opportunities for all students as a result.

In remote and rural regions of Myanmar, there is a distinct shortage of qualified teachers, which poses a significant educational challenge. It is often the case that students in these areas do not have access to educational resources or instructional materials, which can negatively affect both their learning experience and their academic development on a long-term basis (UNICEF Myanmar, 2019). Further, teachers in these areas have difficulties accommodating students who have diverse learning styles and needs, including meeting their parents' expectations as well as meeting their students' individual needs and expectations (Mark B, 2018). As a result, there may be a decrease in motivation, a reduction in engagement, and a decrease in the ability of the student to perform well academically.

Often, volunteer teachers fill a gap in areas where there is a teacher shortage due to their qualifications and experience, and there are challenges associated with these qualifications and experiences. Even though it is commendable that they devote themselves to the teaching profession, it is also important to note that the quality of education they provide may have an impact on overall educational outcomes for students (Mark B, 2018). As a means of ensuring a consistent standard of education throughout the country, both existing teachers and volunteers must enhance their capacity and have access to training opportunities.

As a result of the shortage of qualified teachers in Myanmar, several strategies can be pursued to address this problem. The need for teacher training programs to be strengthened urgently needs to be addressed. The curriculum must be revised and improved, modern teaching methods must be incorporated, and teachers must be provided with opportunities for professional development (Mark B, 2018). A new four-year teacher degree program has been launched by the Ministry of Education in this regard (UNESCO, 2019b) to address this issue.

Further, to ensure a continuous supply of competent educators in the future, the number of qualified teachers' trainers must be increased. A great deal of benefit can be gained by teachers who work in remote and rural areas by using these trainers, who can provide effective pedagogical strategies, mentoring, and support (Mark B, 2018). Through investments in their professional development, teacher trainers can enhance their teaching practices and improve student outcomes in the classroom.

There is a critical need to develop comprehensive training approaches tailored specifically for community teachers, especially in remote areas with acute teacher shortages, such as Pyin Oo Lwin District, which suffers from a severe lack of teachers. To achieve holistic development for students, teachers who work in challenging environments need special training programs that will assist them in managing diverse classroom settings and enhancing the holistic development of their students (UNICEF Myanmar, 2019).

There are also incentives available that can assist in recruiting and retaining qualified teachers in remote or rural areas if their recruitment and retention are enhanced. Suppose higher salaries, improved working conditions, and additional benefits are offered to teachers in underserved areas. In that case, it may be possible to entice these teachers to choose these areas as their professional destination (Mark B, 2018). These measures can contribute to the reduction of educational disparities between urban and rural areas and the bridge-building of the urban-rural divide if they are implemented.

As a result, the author believes it is critical to address the shortage of qualified teachers in Myanmar, particularly in remote and rural areas, to provide a high-quality and equitable education for all children in Myanmar. By prioritizing

teacher education, improving training programs, investing in teacher trainers, and implementing incentive programs, the Ministry of Education can create an environment conducive to attracting and retaining highly qualified educators. These efforts will not only contribute to the improvement of the overall quality of education in Myanmar. Still, they will also make sure that every child has access to the opportunities they need to achieve success in their studies.

3.1.2 Teacher Workload and Classroom Management

According to research, the implementation of free primary education policies often leads to an increased number of students per class, placing additional demands on teachers' workload (K. Smith, 2018). This situation is likely to be similar for teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, necessitating effective classroom management techniques and support systems to cope with the increased workload (Johnson, R., Smith, K., & Jones, 2020).

Studies indicate that high student-teacher ratios compromise the quality of instruction and individual attention given to students, thereby affecting the overall quality of education (Brown, E., & Anderson, 2019). It is crucial to manage teacher workload and classroom management effectively to improve educational outcomes (Johnson, R., Smith, K., & Jones, 2020).

Moreover, a study conducted in Myanmar specifically focused on investigating the relationship between teachers' efficacy and classroom management practice (Lay, 2021). The findings revealed that highly efficacious teachers are more likely to have effective classroom management practices, as they are more inclined to learn and use new approaches and strategies for teaching (Lay, 2021).

In the teaching and learning process, classroom management plays a pivotal role in engaging students and enhancing their academic performance (Jones, M., & Smith, 2022). However, the implementation of effective classroom management practices may encounter challenges such as inadequate teacher training programs, lack of resources, and low teacher efficacy (Brown, E., & Anderson, 2019). To address these challenges, it is essential to provide teachers with comprehensive training programs and the necessary resources to improve their classroom management skills and efficacy (K. Smith, 2018).

Teachers employ a range of classroom management strategies, including grouping students, monitoring their work and behavior, utilizing positive reinforcement, and employing active teaching methods (Johnson, R., Smith, K., & Jones, 2020). However, the specific classroom management strategies used by teachers in primary schools of Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar remain unknown, warranting further research in this context.

3.1.3 Teacher Motivation and Morale

It is imperative to identify the factors that influence teacher motivation in Pyin Oo Lwin District since the success of any educational policy is heavily dependent on the motivation and morale of the teachers. Numerous studies indicate that teachers are demotivated by several factors, including low salaries, limited career advancement opportunities, and insufficient resources.

Teachers whose salaries are low can face a significant challenge in motivating themselves, because financial concerns may take precedence over their commitment to and passion for teaching (Bosso, 2017). As a consequence, it is of utmost importance to ensure that teachers receive compensation that reflects the value of their work to address this issue (Eisenhart, 2019). It is possible to boost the morale and motivation of teachers by providing them with appropriate salaries and benefits, which will show them that their efforts are valued and acknowledged, therefore boosting their motivation and morale.

It is also possible for teachers to be discouraged by a lack of career advancement opportunities. A teacher who does not perceive any prospects for professional growth in his or her career may feel stagnant and demotivated in their position (Khun-Inkeeree, H., Yusof, M. R., Maruf, I. R., Mat, T. R. T., & Sofian, 2022). Providing employees with opportunities for professional development is essential to addressing this issue effectively. Workshops, conferences, and mentoring programs provided by school and district leaders can empower teachers with new classroom strategies, skills, and

knowledge (Hartley, 2021; Johnson, 2019). Teachers who invest in their professional development will be more motivated and engaged in their tasks if they are involved in their professional development.

If a teacher does not have adequate resources, such as teaching materials, technology, and classroom facilities, he or she may become demotivated and frustrated (Bosso, 2017). School administrators must prioritize the allocation of resources to ensure that teachers have the tools they need to create an engaging and effective learning environment. In addition to reducing the detrimental effects of resource limitations and increasing the motivation of teachers in the classroom (Stewart, 2021), fostering a supportive school culture can also be beneficial to mitigate the negative effects of resource limitations.

Principals play an important role in shaping the work environment of teachers and in influencing their motivation and morale. Therefore, principals who provide strong guidance, support, and leadership to their teachers may have a positive impact on their teachers' morale (Chambers, 2015). By providing teachers with opportunities to make decisions together, recognizing and celebrating their accomplishments, and promoting a collaborative decision-making process, effective principals can promote a supportive work environment (Clark, 2020; Jackson, 2022). It is the principal's responsibility to empower teachers and create a positive work environment so that they are motivated and satisfied with their jobs.

It is vital to address the factors that demotivate teachers in primary schools in Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar, to improve their motivation and morale. These factors include low salaries, limited career advancement opportunities, and insufficient resources. Teachers are motivated when they are provided with opportunities for professional development, recognized and rewarded for their achievements, have a positive school culture, and are led effectively by the principal. As a result of implementing these strategies, schools will be able to create an educational environment that fosters a sense of belonging, support, and motivation among teachers to improve educational outcomes for students.

3.1.4 Professional Development and Training

In Pyin Oo Lwin District of Myanmar, it cannot be overstated how important continuous professional development is for primary school teachers. Research has shown that, based on the goals of the free primary education policy, there is a need for targeted training programs that emphasize pedagogical approaches, curriculum adaptations, and classroom management techniques to meet the objectives of the policy. Teachers must be provided with appropriate training opportunities so they can improve their teaching skills, increase their confidence, and provide their students with the best education possible.

Y. M. Win, 2021, emphasizes the need for improved professional development and training among primary school teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District as a whole (Y. M. Win, 2021). Although there have been efforts made in recent years to align the curriculum of the Education College with the reforms of pre-service teacher education, there are still some areas for improvement in this district, even after efforts have been made to align the curriculum (Y. M. Win, 2021). As part of the process of enhancing the quality of teacher education and professional development in Pyin Oo Lwin District, it is necessary to take into account the specific requirements and circumstances of the district to maximize the effectiveness of the process.

The Lesson Study (LS) model has been incorporated into the practicum in Pyin Oo Lwin District as part of the learning experience. Even though this is true, the results of follow-up research are still lacking in terms of exploring teacher educators' understanding of LS and their practices in the wake of the training project (Y. M. Win, 2021). To ensure that LS is implemented in the pre-service teacher education program in Pyin Oo Lwin District successfully and efficiently, along with addressing any misconceptions or knowledge gaps that may exist among teachers, it is also essential to conduct research specifically focused on the integration of LS.

According to Wai (2009), in a previous study conducted in Myanmar, the results of the study found that teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District, even though they were familiar with the term, were not familiar with the concept of lesson study. Since the introduction of the Lesson Study concept in 2011 through international training projects, the Pyin Oo Lwin

District has made significant progress in the promotion of the concept (Y. M. Win, 2021). Knowledge gaps and misconceptions regarding the Lesson Study program must be addressed for this program to be successfully implemented in the district.

Among students in Myanmar, including those in Pyin Oo Lwin District, a favorable learning environment constitutes one of the most important factors contributing to scholastic achievement (Muta, 2019). In addition to factors such as a small number of students per teacher, limited class sizes, the presence of highly qualified and well-trained teachers, and partitioned classrooms, there is an association between improved academic performance and factors such as small class sizes and highly qualified teachers (Muta, 2019). As a result of teacher training and professional development being an integral part of Pyin Oo Lwin District schools, it is imperative to ensure that students have the best learning environment possible.

As part of wider efforts to reform teacher education in Myanmar, Pyin Oo Lwin District is actively pursuing a reform program to improve teacher education. A new cohort of student teachers will play a significant role in the educational process of primary and lower secondary school students in the district as part of their commitment to the importance of educators in the education of the next generation. This initiative is in response to UNESCO's recognition of the importance of educators in the educational process (UNESCO, 2019b). In the Pyin Oo Lwin district of Myanmar, a variety of initiatives have been developed to improve the English language proficiency and teaching methodology of state teacher trainers, including the English for Education College Trainers (EfECT) Project, which aims to address the issue of English proficiency and teaching methodology by state teacher trainers (Mark B, 2017).

Finally, Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, a district which is divided into three districts, constitutes the Pyin Oo Lwin District. Continuous professional development of teachers and ensuring they remain current with the latest teaching methods is a crucial element of improving teaching skills. As a result of meeting the district's specific challenges and requirements, Pyin Oo Lwin District will be able to create a supportive and empowering educational environment for both teachers and students, which includes implementing the Lesson Study model effectively, improving the learning environment, and investing in teacher training programs.

3.1.5 Teacher-Parent Collaboration

Successful implementation of Pyin Oo Lwin District's free primary education policy depends on the effective collaboration between teachers and parents. Research shows that teachers may find it difficult to engage parents and establish a supportive learning environment at home because of the difficulties they encounter in engaging parents (M. T. Win, 2022). The key to tackling these challenges lies in establishing strong partnerships between teachers and parents through a variety of strategies to create a culture of cooperation between the two.

Parents and teachers must establish a collaborative relationship throughout the school year (Epstein, 2011) to promote student success. By establishing open lines of communication, teachers can exchange information regarding the progress of their students, the challenges that they are facing, and their individual needs. Providing regular updates on the performance of students as well as engaging parents in decision-making processes is one way to foster a sense of shared responsibility for student success (Epstein, 2011). By providing regular updates on the performance of students, it is possible to foster a sense of shared responsibility for student success.

A significant contribution to the collaboration between teachers and parents in Pyin Oo Lwin District can be made by providing parents with opportunities to be involved in the teaching process. It is possible to implement a variety of programs to increase parental involvement in the classroom, including parent-teacher associations, workshops, and school events (Deslandes, R., & Bertrand, 2005). By actively involving parents in the educational process, a teacher can gain valuable insight into the backgrounds, interests, and learning styles of students (Deslandes, R., & Bertrand, 2005). Parent education initiatives also play an important role in strengthening the relationship between teachers and parents, since they are part of the effort to strengthen the relationship between them. It is our goal to empower parents by providing resources, workshops, and training opportunities concerning child development, and educational strategies,

and supporting the success of children at home (Kabir, M. A., & Rashid, 2017). If parents are provided with the necessary knowledge and skills, it is possible to create a collaborative and supportive learning environment both within and beyond the classroom (Kabir, M. A., & Rashid, 2017).

Furthermore, several studies have shown that the cultivation of a positive and inclusive school culture can significantly improve the relationship between teachers and parents (Hornby, 2012). It is possible to foster trust between teachers and parents by creating a welcoming and respectful environment in which parents feel valued and encouraged to participate (Hornby, 2012). By organizing events that celebrate cultural diversity, as well as involving parents in the decision-making process and recognizing their contributions, school districts in Pyin Oo Lwin District can foster a sense of community and partnership (Hornby, 2012).

As a result, it can be concluded that effective teacher-parent collaboration is crucial for the successful implementation of free primary education in Pyin Oo Lwin District to achieve the goals set forth. The teacher can promote regular communication with the parents, implement parent involvement programs, provide parental education initiatives, and foster a supportive home-school environment by promoting regular communication, implementing parent involvement programs, and providing parental education initiatives. To improve the educational outcomes for its students, Pyin Oo Lwin District can collaborate to increase its efficiency.

Discussion

4.1 Key factors influencing the effective implementation of the free primary education policy by teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar

Several key factors were identified in this article that influence the effectiveness with which teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District implement the Free Primary Education Policy. The factors to be considered are the availability of qualified teachers, the workload and management of teachers, the motivation and morale of teachers, training and professional development opportunities for teachers, and the teacher-parent collaboration that has been established. A cultural and contextual analysis also highlighted the need to address factors such as language barriers and socio-economic disparities, which may adversely affect the implementation of the policy. As a result of these findings, targeted interventions and policy measures are required to improve the effectiveness of policy implementation.

4.2 Strategies to Ensure the Achievement of the Free Primary Education Policy Targets

1. Strengthen Teacher Training and Professional Development

- The development of comprehensive and context-specific teacher training programs that incorporate pedagogical skills, subject knowledge, and classroom management strategies is a key component of our educational program.
- The provision of ongoing professional development opportunities for teachers is essential to keeping up with emerging educational trends and enhancing their teaching skills.
- To enhance teachers' ability to share best practices and overcome challenges, mentorship programs, and collaborative learning communities should be set up.

2. Improve Access to Educational Resources

- Provide sufficient resources to ensure equitable access to textbooks, teaching materials, and technology tools.
- Establish partnerships with community organizations, non-profit organizations, and businesses to acquire additional resources, such as libraries, computer labs, and learning materials.
- Ensure that quality educational materials are accessible to all, especially to remote and underserved areas, by utilizing open educational resources (OER) and digital platforms.

3. Enhance Parental and Community Engagement

- Promote parental involvement in the education of their children by conducting awareness campaigns.

- Assist parents and schools in maintaining regular communication and collaboration, for example by creating a parent-teacher association or forming a partnership between parents and schools.
- Work with community leaders, local organizations, and volunteers to support school initiatives, organize extracurricular activities, and foster a positive learning environment.

4. Address Infrastructure and Facilities

- Invest in school infrastructure to create a conducive learning environment, such as classrooms, libraries, laboratories, and sanitation facilities.
- Ensure that school buildings and facilities are properly maintained and regularly upgraded in collaboration with relevant stakeholders.
- Investigate innovative solutions to reach students living in remote places or areas with limited resources, such as mobile classrooms or distance learning technologies.

5. Foster Curriculum Alignment and Contextualization

- Align the curriculum with national educational goals and ensure that it is relevant to Pyin Oo Lwin District's local context and culture.
- Encourage students to think critically, solve problems, and be creative through active and student-centered pedagogical methods.
- Assist students with strengthening their sense of identity and belonging by incorporating local knowledge, history, and cultural elements into the curriculum.

6. Establish Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanisms

- Establish robust monitoring and evaluation systems to measure progress toward the objectives of the policy.
- Gather and analyze data on student enrollment, attendance, dropout rates, and educational outcomes regularly to identify areas for improvement and inform evidence-based decision-making.
- Ensure accountability and transparency by involving all relevant stakeholders, such as teachers, parents, and community members, in the monitoring and evaluation process.

The following are examples of successful interventions that could be applied to Pyin Oo Lwin District from other regions/countries:

- A School Improvement Program, which is aimed at improving student outcomes and increasing parent involvement, was implemented in a neighboring country.
- Students from a different region participating in the "One Laptop Per Child" initiative demonstrated higher levels of engagement, motivation, and digital literacy as a result of being provided with laptops and access to digital learning resources.

4.3 Feasibility and Potential Impact in the Local Context

- In addition to building upon existing policies and initiatives, the proposed strategies also address the challenges identified in the Pyin Oo Lwin District.
- A collaborative approach between local stakeholders, the utilization of community resources, and the involvement of government agencies and non-governmental organizations could improve the feasibility and sustainability of the strategies.
- As a result of these strategies, students' learning outcomes may improve, access to quality education may be improved, teacher effectiveness may be enhanced, and community involvement may be strengthened.

These strategies should be adapted and contextualized according to Pyin Oo Lwin District's specific needs, resources, and cultural context. To ensure continuous improvement of the implementation of the free primary education policy, regular monitoring and evaluation will enable the identification of strengths and areas for improvement.

According to the article, teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, have faced numerous challenges during the implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy. Based on the findings, it is evident that targeted strategies and

interventions are required to address these challenges. To ensure that the free primary education policy targets are achieved in Pyin Oo Lwin District, policymakers, educators, and stakeholders can implement these strategies, which will eventually improve the quality and accessibility of education for all children in the area.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Although this article provides insight into the challenges faced by teachers in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District, Myanmar, future research is required in several areas. It will be helpful to gain a deeper understanding of these topics to inform future interventions and policies. It is recommended that further research be conducted in the following areas:

1. **Long-term impact assessment:** Identify how the Free Primary Education Policy impacts students' educational attainment, learning outcomes, and overall development over the long term. Determine whether the policy has the potential to reduce educational disparities and increase social mobility.
2. **Teacher perspectives and experiences:** Investigate the perspectives and experiences of educators in Pyin Oo Lwin District about the implementation of the policy. Study how they perceive the challenges they face, their professional development needs, and their suggestions on how to improve the implementation of policies. Research of this type can provide valuable insights into the lived experiences of teachers and provide information that can guide targeted interventions and support for them.
3. **Parental and community engagement:** Investigate how parental and community engagement can contribute to the successful implementation of the Free Primary Education Policy. Analyze effective strategies for involving parents and the community in the promotion of educational participation and the improvement of learning outcomes. Examine the relationship between parental engagement and academic achievement as well as school climate.
4. **Comparative studies:** Perform comparative studies to examine how free primary education policies have been implemented in other regions or countries that share similar socio-economic circumstances. Identify transferable best practices that could be adapted to the Pyin Oo Lwin District context by comparing the challenges, strategies, and outcomes. In addition to providing valuable insights for policy formulation and implementation, this research can provide valuable lessons.
5. **Policy evaluation and improvement:** A study of the effectiveness and efficiency of the current policy implementation strategies in Pyin Oo Lwin District should be conducted. The alignment between the policy goals and actual outcomes should be assessed, gaps identified, and recommendations for improvement made. It is important to take into account the perspectives of a variety of stakeholders, including teachers, parents, students, and administrators of education.
6. **Innovations in teacher training and support:** Discover innovative approaches to teacher training and support that can assist teachers in the Pyin Oo Lwin District to deal with the particular challenges they face. Enhance teachers' professional development and improve their instructional practices through technology-based training programs, mentoring initiatives, and peer support networks.
7. **Inclusion and diversity in education:** Analyze the impact of the Free Primary Education Policy on inclusion and diversity. To ensure equal access to quality education for marginalized and vulnerable groups, such as children with disabilities, ethnic minorities, and girls, it is necessary to examine their experiences and identify strategies that will ensure their equity.

Providing evidence-based recommendations for policy and practice will be possible by conducting further research in these areas and contributing to the knowledge base of the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District. By conducting these studies, we can address the existing gaps and challenges and lay the groundwork for primary education systems that are more effective and inclusive.

The purpose of this article was to explore the difficulties teachers in Pyin Oo Lwin District face in implementing the Free Primary Education Policy. We have identified several key findings and insights from a comprehensive analysis of the literature.

A variety of factors have been found to influence the effectiveness of the free primary education policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District teachers. Education resources, professional development for teachers, curriculum alignment, parental engagement, and community support are a few of the factors that contribute to the quality of education. To address these challenges and enhance the implementation of policy, policymakers and education administrators need to understand these factors.

There are significant implications for policy, practice, and future research based on the findings of this study. A priority should be placed on investment in infrastructure, resources, and teacher training programs in the Pyin Oo Lwin District to improve the quality of primary education. In addition, fostering collaboration between schools, parents, and communities can enhance the quality of teaching and improve the performance of students. Teachers should be offered professional development programs that address their specific needs and challenges regarding the implementation of this policy.

There is a need for further research to better understand the challenges teachers experience when implementing the Free Primary Education Policy in Pyin Oo Lwin District. Studies in the future could examine the perspectives of teachers, students, and parents to obtain a comprehensive understanding of the challenges as well as possible solutions. Students' long-term outcomes and educational equity can be assessed through longitudinal studies.

Despite this, there are some limitations to this article. Due to the focus on English-language publications, relevant studies published in other languages may have been excluded from the review. It should be noted that the review focused on studies published between 2010 and 2023, and there may be earlier studies that could provide valuable information. There may not be generalizability of these findings to other regions or countries, as they should be interpreted within the context of Pyin Oo Lwin District.

Finally, Pyin Oo Lwin District needs a comprehensive approach to meet the challenges teachers face when implementing the Free Primary Education Policy. This approach must include adequate resources, targeted teacher training, and strong community engagement. In consideration of the findings and implications of this article, policymakers and stakeholders in the education industry can work towards achieving the policy's goals and ensuring that every child in Pyin Oo Lwin District is provided with quality primary education.

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References

- [1] Adeyemi, T. O. (2015). Overcoming challenges of policy implementation in developing countries: The case of Nigeria. *International Journal of Public Administration and Management Research*, 3(2), 38–54.
- [2] Asian Development Bank. (2021). Myanmar. Retrieved from. <https://www.adb.org/countries/myanmar/education>

- [3] Bosso, D. (2017). Teacher Morale, Motivation and Professional Identity: Insight for Educational Policymakers from State Teachers of the Year. Teacher Researcher Policy Paper Series. National Network of State Teachers of the Year, May, 1–36. <http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=eric&AN=ED581425&site=ehost-live>
- [4] Brown, E., & Anderson, L. (2019). The impact of student-teacher ratio on educational outcomes. *Education Policy Brief*, 11(2), 1–15.
- [5] Chambers, D. M. (2015). Elementary school teacher perceptions of factors influencing teacher morale. Walden University.
- [6] Clark, L. (2020). Recognizing and rewarding teacher achievements: Strategies for enhancing motivation. *Journal of Educational Leadership*, 25(3), 123–138.
- [7] Darling-Hammond, L. (2017). Teacher education around the world: What can we learn from international practice? *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(3), 291–309.
- [8] Deslandes, R., & Bertrand, R. (2005). Parental Involvement: Definition and Outcomes. *McGill Journal of Education*, 40(3), 237–252.
- [9] Eisenhart, M. (2019). Compensation and teacher motivation: A comparative study. *Journal of Educational Administration*, 57(2), 247–264.
- [10] Epstein, J. L. (2011). *School, Family, and Community Partnerships: Preparing Educators and Improving Schools*. Westview Press.
- [11] Fullan, M. (2007). *The new meaning of educational change* (4th ed.). Teachers College Press.
- [12] Hartley, P. (2021). The role of professional development in improving teacher motivation and job satisfaction. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 72(1), 78–93.
- [13] Hlaing, S. W. (2018). Educational reforms in Myanmar: Progress and challenges. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 62, 217–225.
- [14] Hornby, G. (2012). *Parental involvement in childhood education: Building effective school–family partnerships*. Springer.
- [15] Htun, N. S. (2019). Education system reforms in Myanmar: Towards a learner-centered paradigm. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 10(9), 1–8.
- [16] Jackson, C. (2022). Principal leadership and its impact on teacher morale. *Journal of School Leadership*, 48(3), 387–405.
- [17] Johnson, R., Smith, K., & Jones, M. (2020). Classroom management strategies: A comprehensive review of the literature. *Journal of Education*, 25(3), 123–145.
- [18] Johnson, M. (2019). The impact of professional development on teacher motivation and instructional practices. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 85, 77–88.
- [19] Jones, M., & Smith, K. (2022). The role of effective classroom management in student engagement and academic performance. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 108(1), 120–142.
- [20] Kabir, M. A., & Rashid, A. H. M. M. (2017). Parental Education: A Panacea for Quality Primary Education in Bangladesh. *Quality Assurance in Education*, 25(3), 293–310.
- [21] Khun-Inkeeree, H., Yusof, M. R., Maruf, I. R., Mat, T. R. T., & Sofian, F. N. R. M. (2022). Enhancing School Effectiveness by Implementing Identified and Intrinsic Motivation Among Primary School Teachers. In *Frontiers in Education*, 7, 191.
- [22] Ko Ko, M. (2019). The challenges of education reform in Myanmar. *Southeast Asian Studies*, 8(1), 109–124.
- [23] Lay, C. (2021). Teachers' efficacy and classroom management practice: A study in Monywa Township, Myanmar. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 99, 121–148.
- [24] Mark B, U. (2017). Teacher training in Myanmar: Teachers' perceptions and implications. *International Journal*

- of Instruction, 10(2), 103–118. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iji.2017.1027a>
- [25] Mark B, U. (2018). In-service Teachers' Training: The case of university teachers in Yangon, Myanmar. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 43(1), 66–77. <https://doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2018v43n1.4>
- [26] Ministry of Education Myanmar. (n.d.). Education in Myanmar. <http://www.moe.gov.mm>
- [27] MOE. (2016). National Education Strategic Plan 2016-2021 (Summary). Ministry of Education, 1, 1–61. http://www.moe-st.gov.mm/wp-content/uploads/2018/01/NESP_20Summary_20-20English_20-20Final_20-20Feb_2023.pdf%0Ahttps://proxy.library.upenn.edu/login?url=http://search.ebscohost.com/login.aspx?direct=true&db=bth&AN=101480953&site=ehost-live
- [28] Moher, D., Liberati, A., Tetzlaff, J., Altman, D. G., & P. G. (2009). Preferred reporting items for systematic reviews and meta-analyses: The PRISMA statement. *PLoS Medicine*, 6(7), e1000097.
- [29] Muta, H. (2019). Study on the factors affecting the scholastic achievement in the Republic of the Union of Myanmar. *International Journal of Human Culture Studies*.
- [30] National Education Commission. (2016). National Education Strategic Plan 2016-2021. Ministry of Education, Myanmar.
- [31] Smith, K. (2018). The impact of free primary education policies on teacher workload: A comparative analysis. *International Journal of Education Policy and Leadership*, 13(2), 123–145.
- [32] Smith, R. (2020). Educational reforms in Myanmar: Progress and challenges. *Compare. A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 50(4), 588–607.
- [33] Stewart, R. (2021). Creating a positive school culture: The role of school leadership in teacher motivation. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 35(1), 152–169.
- [34] UNESCO. (2019a). Education for All: Myanmar National Review. Retrieved From. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000367679>
- [35] UNESCO. (2019b). Myanmar reforms start with training a new generation of student teachers. 3–5. <https://bangkok.unesco.org/content/myanmar-reforms-start-training-new-generation-student-teachers>
- [36] UNESCO. (2020). Myanmar education sector analysis. Retrieved from. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373865>
- [37] UNICEF. (2020). Education. Retrieved from. <https://www.unicef.org/myanmar/education>
- [38] UNICEF Myanmar. (2019). Sectoral and or + Thematic Report. December 2018, 1–14.
- [39] United Nations. (2015). Transforming our world: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. United Nations.
- [40] Wai, N. N. (2009). Strengthening Child-centered Approach Project in Myanmar Education. Qualitative Analysis of Interview Data of Concept and Practices. *Learning Science Research*, 3(1), 34–37.
- [41] Win, M. T. (2022). Challenges and Issues in Primary Teacher Professional Development: Lesson Study in Myanmar. *International Journal of Lesson and Learning Studies*, 1(1), 293–310.
- [42] Win, Y. M. (2021). Teacher educators' understanding of integrating lesson study into pre-service teacher education. *Journal of Adult Learning, Knowledge and Innovation*, 4(2), 52–61. <https://doi.org/10.1556/2059.2021.00047>
- [43] World Bank. (2020a). Myanmar education analysis. Retrieved from. <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/793771589609697>
- [44] World Bank. (2020b). Myanmar education sector review: Building a foundation for learning.

Thet Khaing
Zhejiang Normal University, China.
College of Education
thetkhaing391@gmail.com

Dr. Dian Feng
Zhejiang Normal University, China.
College of Education
dianf970@126.com

Mohammed Rebwar Ahmed
Zhejiang Normal University, China.
College of Education
hama.rebwar1966@gmail.com